

Becoming a self-employed RSE web developer.

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Software

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1 Teri Apps

This is a two part talk, initially focussing on how I changed career and established a sole trader business, the second part on the latest web development techniques I use.

Early last year I started doing additional web and mobile app development in my evenings and weekends, leading me to start my own sole trader business. In January I became self-employed full time, leaving my RSE job at the University of Leicester to begin contract work for the Wellcome Trust DataLabs. In this talk I will cover the pros and cons of this kind of career change, the lessons I learnt and personal skills required to make the jump. Exposure to this kind of RSE career change would hopefully be insightful and useful to all attendees thinking about their future careers.

The second part of my talk will focus on the latest web development techniques that myself and colleagues use at the Wellcome Trust. We're currently building a data sharing platform for universities and funders as part of the Research on Research Institute (RoRI). I will walk through how a modern web/app development project is set up, the options for languages and frameworks at each stage and what we're using to build the RoRI platform. I will also discuss how this relates to mobile app development. From this part of the talk attendees should gain some basic knowledge on how modern web and app development is done, and how they can apply these techniques to their own RSE projects.

My talk would suit a broad target audience as it covers both RSE careers and some wide ranging techniques. As both web and mobile app development are listed in the wishlist I believe there is an interest in the community for a talk such as this.